

Optimization algorithm applied to extended range fuel cell hybrid vehicles. Contribution to road transport decarbonization

Oriana Perez-Dávila^a, Roberto Álvarez Fernández^a

Universidad Nebrija Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Progressive decarbonization of road transport is underway to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and their harmful effects. Although different options have already been considered, hydrogen-electric hybridization seems to be an interesting option to reduce emissions by offering vehicles with a sufficient range and competitive performance compared to current fossil fuel vehicles. The development of energy management systems (EMS) that achieve efficient use of energy is crucial to extend the range that a vehicle can achieve. In this paper we propose two different energy management systems applied to two hydrogen hybrid vehicles: a Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV) and a Range Extender-Electric Vehicle (EREV). Both proposed EMS implement a rule-based strategy (RBS) which distributes the current demanded by the motor between the fuel cell and the battery. The EMS parameters for both approaches were selected using a particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm in order to find the optimized set of values for both EMS. The proposals have been tested for different driving cycles and the results obtained show a 7 % and 5 % improvement in range (and consequent reduction in GHG emissions) for both EMS proposals respectively when compared to previous work.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Two rule-based energy management strategies (single and multi-level) are proposed to distribute the current demanded by the motor between the fuel cell and the battery for the hydrogen hybrid vehicles.
- A particle swarm optimization algorithm (PSO) is applied to both proposed energy management strategies to compute the best set of control variables that improve the range achieved by the vehicle and the energy it consumes.
- The two proposed EMSs were integrated into two different powertrain configurations (FC-PHEV, FC- EREV).
- Extensive simulation campaigns were conducted in order to validate the proposed EMSs under different working conditions, showing improvements in terms of increase of achieved range under different driving profiles and reduction in the energy consumed.

INTRODUCTION

The electrification of road transport is a topic that has concerned not only governments but also the research community with greater intensity during the past 10-12 years. The transportation sector is responsible of approximately 15 % of the total greenhouse gas emissions and the global CO₂ (Friedlingstein et al., 2014)

problem. Dependence on fossil fuels (Egbue and Long, 2012) as the main energy source in transportation causes most of the emissions, and then it constitutes the main problem to tackle (Weiss et al., 2012). Many car manufacturing companies have promoted and developed technologies to progressively replace the conventional internal combustion vehicle fleet with cleaner energy-powered vehicles. In this context, Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV), powered solely by a rechargeable electric battery, represents today the most extended carbon-free transportation mode (Javaid et al., 2020). However, there are still numerous customer barriers such as limited range, the requirement for multiple charging events during long trips, the time required for these charging events as well as the slow development of a public charging infrastructure, that make these vehicles unattractive to users (Fernandez, 2021). An attempt to extend the range capability is the hybrid vehicles, powered by a combination of electricity and fossil fuels. Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) combine the internal combustion engine along with an electric motor powered by a battery that is charged from the internal combustion engine. The Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV) represented a step forward, with an increase of the battery capacity and including the possibility of charging the battery in plug-in mode directly from the electric grid (Rahman et al., 2015). Finally, the Extended-Range Electric Vehicles (EREVs) run using electricity such as a BEV, although the internal combustion engine included is used to recharge the battery and sustain it within levels that optimize its performance (Brand et al., 2017; Vasant et al., 2016). Although these hybrid vehicles solve part of the barriers and help reducing greenhouse gas emissions, the fact is that they still using fossil fuels and these vehicles are not zero direct emissions to the environment. The demand for BEVs and PHEVs has been continuously increasing while European Union (EU) registrations sales of traditional fossil fuel cars are decreasing (ACEA, 2021).

Hydrogen has been considered a low-carbon energy that can be produced without generating greenhouse gas emissions to the environment by using renewable electricity sources (Samsatli and Samsatli, 2019). To generate electricity from hydrogen it is necessary to use a Fuel Cell (FC), which is a device that uses hydrogen and oxygen to create electric current. Vehicles based on hydrogen, Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs), are available in the market and they have been considered a clean replacement for internal combustion engines (NEESC, 2018) due to their multiples advantages: high efficiency, low-operation noises and zero direct emissions (Sharaf and Orhan, 2014; Un-Noor et al., 2017). The main drawbacks of this technology are the insufficient hydrogen fueling infrastructure, high cost as well as hydrogen storage and safety. Although at the end of 2020, 540 Hydrogen Refueling Stations (HRS) were in operation worldwide with an increase of 15 % with respect to 2019 (IEA, 2021), it seems to be not enough to make this alternative attractive to customers. A key factor to promote market penetration of hydrogen-fueled cars lies in hybridization. While Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) incorporate a low-capacity battery that helps power the vehicle and recover energy from regenerative braking, Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicles (FCHEVs) increase the battery energy storage and allows to plug it. Hybridization solves the range barriers of the BEV and achieves improvements in weight, battery lifetime, and charge times (Sulaiman et al., 2018). From the original FCHEV concept, they can be derived two main powertrains: Plug-in Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (FC-PHEV) and Range Extended Fuel Cell Hybrid Vehicle (Álvarez Fernández et al., 2016). The first one uses the electricity stored in the battery to power the vehicle until it is exhausted and then, the electricity generated

through the fuel cell is used. On the other hand, the FC-EREV uses hydrogen to recharge the battery and to help power the vehicle when the power demanded is too high. The objective is to keep the State of Charge (SoC) within a predefined band. The development of a suitable Energy Management Strategy (EMS) for this powertrain is crucial to find a proper balance between the limited range offered by the energy storage devices and the high cost of the hydrogen.

This paper is a continuation of previous works published by the authors (Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2016; Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2018; Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022). In particular, the latter proposed a rule-based system and a novel procedure for estimating the energy consumption of these vehicles. The following step is presented in this paper, where we make use of a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm to optimize the parameters of the EMS. Furthermore, we extend the rules-based EMS model to consider the hydrogen storage tank level in order to change the parameters of the controller. We validate our proposal through an extensive series of simulations applied to the models developed with Simulink and applying multiple driving cycles. The results show how the vehicle range is extended compared with the previous approach (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several energy management strategies have been proposed to solve the power distribution problems in FCHEVs. In (Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2018) a powertrain based on the use of the fuel cell stack as a range-extender system coupled to the standard electric vehicle concept was used. The range and fuel consumption with different energy management strategies were studied by applying different tests, including the approach based on genetic algorithms. Results demonstrated that using this optimization algorithm the proposed powertrain configuration achieves higher ranges. Zhou et al. (2020) developed an adaptive energy management strategy that incorporates a driving pattern recognizer and a multi-mode model predictive controller. At the supervisory level, the Markov pattern recognizer classifies the real-time driving segment into one of three predefined patterns. Based on the periodically updated pattern identification results, one set of pre-optimized control parameters is selected to formulate the multi-objective cost function. Afterward, the desirable control policies are obtained by solving a constrained optimization problem within each prediction horizon. Validation results demonstrated the effectiveness of the Markov with a high identification accuracy and a reduction in the hydrogen consumption. In (Carignano et al., 2019) it is presented an energy management system focused on fuel economy and including aspects of battery degradation. In (Zhang et al., 2021), and EMS for PHEVs with the enhanced adaptability to various traffic conditions is presented by applying a traffic-state identification method. According to the identified traffic conditions, control thresholds are optimized by a chaotic PSO with offline sequential quadratic programming which is updated timely. Results show how the adaption to different traffic conditions, together with the evolved rules-based algorithm, improves the fuel economy. An EMS based on a multi input fuzzy logic controller was presented in (Mahmoodi-k et al., 2021) with a simultaneous multi-objective constrained optimization approach to enhance optimally various coupling design parameters (optimization

variables), design objectives (fuel economy, costs, and emissions), as well as non-linear constraints (vehicle dynamic and batteries performance). The simulation results showed that the proposed instantaneous optimization method and the multi-objective simultaneous optimization algorithm could respectively improve the overall efficiency and achieve a reduction in emissions up to 7 % and 10% for real-world driving cycle and at the same time decrease the operational costs up to 12% approving its applicability. In (Liu et al., 2019) a multi-objective hierarchical prediction strategy is presented to achieve optimal FC life and energy consumption economy for an FC-EREV. A fusion algorithm that combines the direct configuration method and sequential quadratic programming is proposed to achieve both, an optimal FC life and energy consumption economy. Simulation results validate that the proposed strategy can effectively reduce operating costs compared with other strategies. (Fathy et al., 2019) and (Rezk et al., 2021) presented an EMS based on a Salp Swarm Algorithm (SSA). This strategy was compared with commonly used strategies such as fuzzy logic control, classical proportional integral control, state machine approach, equivalent fuel consumption minimization, external energy maximization and, equivalent consumption minimization. Results demonstrated that the proposed SSA-based management strategy performed best compared with all other used strategies in terms of hydrogen fuel economy and overall efficiency.

Following the above considerations available in the literature, this work proposes to combine a rule-based strategy taking into the account the SoC evolution and the hydrogen storage in the tank, applying a PSO algorithm, aiming to find the best powertrain configurations for FC-EREV and PHEVs to improve the range, knowing that this implies a reduction in emissions per kilometer. Applying the control based on rules with a high efficiency achieved (Sorlei et al., 2021), together with the PSO algorithm the decisions are not empirical because the optimization algorithm decides the best battery SoC level where the battery switches from Charge Depleting Mode (CD) to Charge Sustaining Mode (SC) as well as the operation mode for the fuel cell. Previous work (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022), demonstrated that the vehicle range is affected by the powertrain configuration selected, using the PSO it is possible to warrant a configuration that maximizes the vehicle range and reduces CO₂ emissions.

Figure 1: Extended Range / Plug-In Fuel Cell powertrain configuration

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we first describe a basic system model of a fuel-cell based hybrid vehicle which is used to present the proposals made in the paper, showing the basic parts composing the model and how they interact in the two main powertrain models considered in this paper, FC-PHEV and FC-EREV. Then, focusing on how the energy coming from the two suppliers is distributed, we present two EMSs proposals. Finally, we present the optimization approach that is applied to both EMSs and how the best set of parameters are selected for their operation. A strategy to extend the range of FCHEVs is developed. This strategy demonstrates that a vehicle can be benefited in terms of the kilometers covered and energy consumed, if optimized energy management is applied. Two powertrains defined in the literature (Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2016) have been selected to be applied to this strategy, these powertrains are the aforementioned FC-PHEV and FC-EREV. A powertrain comprises the components that deliver the power from the source (batteries, hydrogen, fuel-oil, etc.), passing through the engine/motor that performs the energy conversion to deliver the mechanical power to the wheels of the vehicle. Although this is not exclusive to fuel cell powered vehicles, in the rest of the paper only unless explicitly indicated we will refer as powertrain to FCHEVs. The architecture under analysis is shown in Figure 1, where readers can see how the energy is obtained from two sources, hydrogen tank and li-ion batteries, and managed by the energy management system which delivers current to the electric motor through a power converter and then, the mechanical power goes to the wheels. Hybrid vehicles include an energy recovery system that manages the capability to generate an electric current that is used to recharge the battery whenever is possible. As it can be noted from the discussion above, the way the battery is used is different in both, FC-PHEV and FC-EREV. In Figure 2 we show the expected SoC trajectory for both powertrain configurations. In the case of the FC-EREV (solid line), the vehicle is assumed to start with the battery fully charged (90 %). Then the vehicle starts using battery power until it reaches the low SoC level (point A). After that, the full cell provides a Fuel Cell Recharge Current ($I_{R_{FC}}$) until the battery reaches the programmed high SoC level (Point B). While the vehicle is operating between the sustained band, a positive slope in the SoC corresponds to recharge current coming from the full cell and negative slope corresponds to the battery supplying the current to the motor.

Figure 2: Extended Range / Plug-In SoC behavior

In the FC-PHEV (dotted line), the vehicle is assumed to start with the battery fully charged (90 %). Then

the vehicle starts using battery power until it reaches the low SoC level (point C) selected, this level is around 20 %. After that, the FC provides the current demanded by the motor and an amount of current to keep the battery at this level until the vehicle is connected to a power supply to recharge the battery. Note that although the SoC levels can be set by both configurations, the low SoC level must never be under the absolute minimum SoC (10 %) which put in risk on the integrity of the battery. The values for the high/low SoC levels, as well as the recharge current, have great impact on the range that the vehicle can achieve. Next, we will explain the EMSs proposals to improve the hydrogen consumption and hence the achieved range for the hybrid vehicle.

Energy Management Strategy (EMS)

The EMS proposed for the two powertrain models is a Rule-Based Strategy (RBS) as seen in (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022). There are defined two types of EMS, in the first type, the rules are independent of hydrogen storage while in the second one, the hydrogen storage is considered in the energy distribution decisions.

- **Single SoC Interval (EMS Type 1):** The energy distribution is made through a group of rules that distribute the current requested by the motor supplied by the battery and the fuel cell. These rules are divided into two states: CD and SC. CD refers to the case where the vehicle is operating using mainly the battery, while the FC is only used to supply the peaks of energy demanded by the motor. SC is triggered when the battery reaches a low level and then the FC start supplying both, the motor and a current to recharge the battery. Both states, SC or CD, have four internal rules in order to consider the regenerative braking and the recharge battery current. Figure 3 is shown the system structure around the Current Distribution Block (CDB) which is the block responsible to implement the EMS. As can be seen, the CDB receive the current by the electric motor (I_M), the actual SoC level (SoC_A), and the hydrogen tank level as inputs. Based on the rules, the CDB selects the amount of current that must be supplied by the battery and the FC to fulfill the requirements of the motor. In the beginning, considering the battery is full charged ($SoC > 70\%$), the vehicle operates in CD and then the battery energizes the motor. The CDB considers different sub-cases cases: i) The current required by the motor is within the battery limit: in this case the battery fully energizes the motor; ii) The current demanded exceed the battery limits: in this case, the FC provides the rest of the current needed to satisfy the motor power request. The system operates in CD until the battery reaches a Low-Level State of Charge (SoC_L). At this moment, the system changes from CD to SC mode and then the FC starts supplying not only the current demanded by the electric motor, but also an amount of current to recharge the battery (IR_{FC}). Similar to the CD mode, different sub-cases apply to the system operation: i) The current required by the motor is within the fuel-cell limit: in this case the FC fully energizes the motor and, at the same time, provides the required IR_{FC} to recharge the battery. ii) The current demanded exceeds the FC limits: in this case the FC is solely

used to supply the energy demanded by the motor while the battery provides the rest of I_M . The system operates in SC until the battery reaches a High-Level State of Charge (SoC_H). After that, the system alternates between CD and SC until the hydrogen tank is empty and the battery reaches its minimum safety value as shown in Figure 2. It is worth noticing, that when operating either in CD or SC, the electrical current generated by regenerative braking is used to recharge the battery and then extends the range the vehicle can achieve. The values of SoC_L , SoC_H and IR_{FC} have a great impact on the range the vehicle can achieve and then a proper joint selection of these parameters is important to fully exploit the potential of the system. Later, we will show how these parameters were optimized to extend the vehicle range.

Figure 3: System structure

- Multiple SoC Interval (EMS Type 2):** The EMS Type 1 selects values for SoC_L , SoC_H and IR_{FC} , without taking into account the actual level of the hydrogen tank. That is, the system operates alternatively between CD and SC producing the triangular-like pattern in the SoC-time evolution shown in Figure 2, until the hydrogen tank is empty. To exploit the capabilities of the vehicle we propose a novel EMS that keeps the rules-based strategy but taking into consideration the actual hydrogen tank level in order to select the proper set of SoC_L , SoC_H and IR_{FC} . In this paper we divide the hydrogen tank in different levels according to the amount of hydrogen stored. For each tank level a group of controls variables are defined, this means that the SoC interval and the IR_{FC} changes as hydrogen is used. This way of dividing the tank does not impact significantly the complexity of the implementation and that the same time helps to improve the performance of the system. Specifically, is considered three different levels for the hydrogen tank. For each tank level (l), a different group of parameters is used in the system ($SoC_L(l)$, $SoC_H(l)$ and $IR_{FC}(l)$). The EMS Type 2 operates similarly to the Type 1 introduced above with the following main differences: When the system enters in CD, it reads the hydrogen tank level in order to update the $SoC_L(l)$ value. When

operating in SC mode, the tank level is constantly monitored to select the $SoC_H(l)$ and $IR_{FC}(l)$ values. This is done, because in this mode, the vehicle is mainly powered by the FC and then the tank level could cross to a different zone which would require to update the set of parameters to be used. Similar to EMS Type 1, the performance of the system strongly depends on the set of (multiple) parameters to be selected and then putting extra complexity to the way their values are selected.

Optimization approach

As explained above, the selection of the starting set of parameters for the EMS plays a key impact on the range the vehicle can achieve following a certain trajectory. Despite the different ways that can be implemented to select their values (Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2016; Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022) proposed test a set of parameters without use an optimization algorithm . Although the authors show how the performance of the system is improved, the size of the set is the more complex process to select the best the group of parameters. Aiming to achieve an efficient parameter selection, we propose the use of a particle swarm optimization (PSO).

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimization algorithm motivated by intelligent collective behavior of some animals such as flocks of birds or schools of fish (Wang, 2018). In this paper we use the PSO to find the proper set of parameters ($SoC_L^*(l)$, $SoC_H^*(l)$ and $IR_{FC}^*(l)$) that solves two different optimization problems: the first one is finding the optimum set of values that maximizes vehicle range using all the hydrogen stored in the tank and energy stored in the battery (until its minimum safety SoC value). Note that in the case of the EMS Type 1, the problem reduces to choose the length and position in the y-axis of the sustaining band (Figure 2) and the increasing slope of the SoC level when operating in SC mode. The second optimization problem consists of finding the optimal set of parameters for the EMS that minimizes the vehicle energy consumption during a fixed amount of time. It is important to remark that the internal parameters such as the initial values for the particles, cost functions and the number of particles were particularized for each one of the optimization problems stated above.

Regardless of the EMS type, the first optimization problem to solve is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{maximize} && \text{Range [km]} \\
 & \text{subject to} && IR_{FC}^*(l) \leq Ib_r \\
 & && SoC_L^*(l) \leq SoC_H^*(l) \\
 & && SoC_L^*(l) \geq SoC_{\min} \\
 & && SoC_H^*(l) \leq SoC_{\max}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Where we aim to maximize the range that the vehicle can achieve for a certain driving cycle. In Equation 1

I_{b_r} is the maximum recharge current that can be assumed by the battery, SoC_{min} corresponds to the absolute minimum SoC level the system is allowed to reach and, similarly, the SoC_{max} corresponds to the maximum SoC allowed for the system. Note the Equation 1 can be used for both proposed EMS, since $l=1$ for EMS Type 1 and $l=1:3$ for EMS Type 2 (although system can be extended to support different number of levels). The range that the vehicle can achieve is measured at the time where the hydrogen is exhausted and the battery SoC reaches the SoC_{min} .

As explained above, the second optimization problem consists of reducing the hydrogen consumption in a short route with a fixed duration. In this case, the cost function shown in Equation 2 looks for minimizing the amount of hydrogen (kg) required to travel through the fixed route.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{minimize} \quad KgH_2 \\
 & \text{subject to} \quad IR_{FC}^*(l) \leq Ib_r \\
 & \quad \quad \quad SoC_L^*(l) \leq SoC_H^*(l) \\
 & \quad \quad \quad SoC_L^*(l) \geq SoC_{min} \\
 & \quad \quad \quad SoC_H^*(l) \leq SoC_{max}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Where KgH_2 represents the hydrogen stored in the tank. In Figure 4 the system structure connected to the PSO is shown. Operation PSO-based optimization for a single problem is similar for both optimization problems and for both EMS types. Each particle defines its own set of parameters $\{SoC_L(l)(n,m), SoC_H(l)(n,m), IR_{FC}(l)(n,m)\}$, where n stands for the particle number and m corresponds to the iteration number. The system starts ($m=0$) with the PSO initialization where a first group of values are chosen for each one of the particles. These values are chosen from uniformly distributed random distributions which range is selected to comply with the constraints of the optimization problem to solve. The output of the system after the initialization step is either the range achieved by the vehicle or the hydrogen used to travel through the fixed route for the first or the second optimization problem, respectively. The output of the system is used to update the value of the parameters for each one of the particles as the algorithm progresses.

One important fact to consider is that originally the PSO does not deal with hard constraints, differently from what we stated in Equations (1) and (2) respectively. To deal with this, a simple penalization system that operates independently for each particle n at each iteration m has been proposed. The penalization works as follows: once the PSO updates the parameters and before running the system, it is performed a validation phase where the system checks if the parameter values comply with the constraints. If any of the values do not comply with the constraints, the system does not run for that set of parameters and then the output value is set to very low or very high value whether Equation 1 or Equation 2 optimization problem is running, respectively. This action does not only force the PSO particle to move to a different direction but also helps to speed-up the execution of the algorithm since the system does not compute values that do not comply with the constraints. After running the programmed number of iterations, the PSO returns the

optimum set of parameters [$SoC_L^*(l)$, $SoC_H^*(l)$ and $IR_{FC}^*(l)$] that solve the optimization problem complying with the constraints imposed to the problem.

Figure 4: System structure. PSO algorithm

EXPERIMENTS

In this section we address the simulation framework of the two proposed EMSs. It is described the simulation model and built two different scenarios where the proposal is analyzed.

Simulation Model

The two proposed EMS were tested using a powertrain simulation model developed using Simulink tools from MATLAB. The vehicle dynamics were extracted from the Hyundai ix35 Fuel Cell vehicle which incorporates a 100 kW (134 horsepower) squirrel cage induction motor that offers constant maximum torque of 300 Nm (0 - 3600 rpm) and constant power of 100 kW (3600 - 7200 rpm). Details about the modelled vehicle are presented in Table 1. The battery model was modeled based on the one proposed in (Alvarez Fernandez et al., 2016). This battery has a bigger capacity compared with the one installed in the Hyundai ix35 FCEV, reaching a range around 100 km driving in CD mode (Álvarez Fernández et al., 2018). Table 2 summarizes the most important battery characteristics. The FC stack selected was modelled following the procedures described in (O'Hayre et al., 2016), which have been adapted to the characteristics of the FC installed in the Hyundai ix35. The FC modeled is a Proton Exchange Membrane, which voltage range is 250 V – 450 V, 100 kW of power and composed of 440 cells assembled in lamination. The vehicle

can store 5.64 kg of hydrogen and has a tank capacity of 142 L, pressured at 700 bar.

Table 1: Hyundai ix35 vehicle dynamics data set

Table 2: Battery parameters

Overall Length (mm)	4410
Overall Width (mm)	1820
Overall Height (mm)	1650
Wheelbase (mm)	2640
Front Wheel Tread(mm)	1585
Rear Wheel Tread (mm)	1586
Front Over Hang (mm)	880
Rear Over Hang (mm)	890
Cargo Area (VDA)(litre)	551
Heaviest Curb Weight (kg)	2290
Gross Vehicle Weight (kg)	2290

In order to model both proposed EMS Types, we implemented CDBs as rule based strategy for each one of the powertrain models FC-EREV and FC-PHEV, it is important to remark that the EMS Type 2 was only

Energy content	19 kWh
Capacity (per cell)	50 Ah
Voltage	380 V
Discharge cont. (power)	200 A (80 kW)
Discharge peak. (power)	400 A (160 kW)
Max charging current	80 A

modelled for the FC-EREV model since the FC-PHEV powertrain has identically behavior for both EMS types.

In order to perform the parameter optimization using the PSO algorithm as explained above, we created a simulation top-level function which instantiate the PSO algorithm and computes the set of parameters to be used by each particle at each iteration while the algorithm progresses. When the parameters have been computed, the constraint validation is performed, as explained before. If the values of the parameters fulfil the required constraints, then the top-level function runs the Simulink model that implements the powertrain under test. As it can be seen, this is an iterative process performed for each one of the tests that will be described next. For each test conducted, it is implemented a PSO with 50 particles regardless of the EMS Type being evaluated. The main difference between the two EMS types relies on the number of parameters the PSO needs to be optimized. A list of the PSO parameters is presented in Table 3.

Iterations	50
Particles	50
C1	0.12
C2	1.2
w	0.9

Table 3: PSO internal parameters

We analyzed the proposed EMS Types using the described simulation model for the following scenarios for both FC-EREV and FC-PHEV powertrain models.

- **Scenario 1: Maximum range**

The aim of this scenario is to find the maximum range the vehicle can travel under different driving cycles. The maximum range is measured considering that (at the beginning) the hydrogen tank is full (100%), and the battery charge is at 90%. Then, the vehicle model travel through multiple repetitions of the driving cycle until the hydrogen tank is completely empty and the battery reach the absolute minimum value (10%). Three drive cycles are used to validate the proposed EMS Types for this scenario: World Harmonized Light-duty Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTC) class 2 and class 3 and New European Driving Cycle (NEDC).

- **Scenario 2. Hydrogen consumption minimization**

In this scenario, the simulation model is configured to run over a fixed number of kilometers. Then, the aim is to minimize the use of the available hydrogen in the tank over this short route. In the simulations performed we fix the route length to be 450 km, despite the driving cycle under test. This value is selected to force the vehicle to use both hydrogen and the energy stored in the battery. In this sense, the PSO needs to optimize the parameters to make the best use of the fuels and to minimize the hydrogen consumption.

RESULTS

In this section it is displayed the set or results obtained by the application of the proposed EMS Types on the simulation model for each one of the scenarios and powertrains explained.

SCENARIO 1. FC-EREV

In order to validate the maximum range that the vehicle can achieve, it is configured the simulation environment to try multiple repetitions of each driving cycle applied, such that the number exceed the expected range the vehicle is able to be achieved. That is, the simulation runs until the hydrogen tank is empty and the SoC level is equal to SoC_{min} . To obtain the optimized set of parameters $SoC_{L^*}(l)$, $SoC_{H^*}(l)$ and

$IR_{FC}^*(l)$ we run the PSO with the internal configuration described for both EMS proposals and each driving cycle. For the proposed EMS Type 1 parameter optimization, it has been modified one of the constraints defined in Equation (1) for the FC-EREV case. Instead of simply constraint the $SoC_{L}^*(l)$ value to be higher than the SoC_{min} , we also force the optimization algorithm to choose a value lower than 0.3 (30%). We do this to reinforce the operation of the vehicle in range extender configuration and then taking advantage of the battery size by using a big part of its stored charge before start using the hydrogen. Similarly, for the $SoC_{H}^*(l)$ we force the algorithm to choose a value higher than 0.35 (35%) and lower than SoC_{max} . Then, the algorithm looks for the optimized set of parameters keeping its operation in the range extender configuration. The two modified constraints for the EMS Type 1 are shown in Equation 3.

$$\begin{aligned} SoC_{min} &\leq SoC_{L}^*(l) \leq 0.3 \\ 0.35 &\leq SoC_{H}^*(l) \leq SoC_{max} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: PSO evolution (EMS Type 1)

Figure 6: Range PSO-evolution (EMS Type 1)

As an example, we present how the PSO is able to converge to an optimum solution, maximizing the number of kilometers driven when applying the WLTC class 3 driving cycle as the iterations of the algorithm progresses. Figure 5 shows how $SoCL$ (top), $SoCH$ (middle) and the IR_{FC} (bottom) update their values as the algorithm progresses. Note that we are only presenting the results achieved by the best particle at the end of each iteration number. Similarly, in Figure 6 it is shown the range the vehicle achieves for the parameters displayed in Figure 5. As it can be seen, the range increases as the algorithm progresses, then getting closer to the optimum values. Furthermore, note how the $SoCL$ and $SoCH$ values comply with the modified constraint shown in Equation 3.

In Figure 7 it is presented the SoC versus time evolution for the optimized parameters obtained from the PSO algorithm for the WLTC class 3 driving cycle. To establish a comparison, we also include the plot of the evolution achieved by the RBS approach proposed in (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022). In order

to stress our proposal under different conditions, we also run the optimization algorithm for two extra driving cycles: NEDC and WLTC class 2. Since the length of each driving cycle is different, 23.26, 14.66 and 11 kilometers for the WLTC class 3, WLTC class 2 and the NEDC respectively, we adjust the simulation time, such that we ensure that the hydrogen and tank and the battery charge are fully used at the end of the simulation. In Figure 8 is shown the SoC versus time evolution for the WLTC class 2 (top) and NEDC (bottom) driving cycles using the parameters from the PSO optimization. It is also shown in Figure 8, the SoC-time evolution using the discrete parameter tuning as proposed in (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022).

Figure 7: Battery SoC time evolution for FC-EREV and EMS Type 1. (WLTC class 3 driving cycle)

Figure 8: Battery SoC time evolution for FC-EREV and EMS Type 1 (NEDC and WLTC class 2)

It is important to remark that despite the difference in the driving cycle pattern and how aggressive these could be with the fuel consumption, the EMS Type 1 with PSO-based parameter optimization is able to exhaust the available fuel well time after the RBS approach which directly translate to more driving cycles and then to more kilometers travelled. In Table 4 the values of the SoC_L^* , SoC_H^* and IR_{FC}^* parameters returned by the PSO algorithm and the number of kilometers the vehicle travels for each of the driving cycles under test are displayed.

Drive cycle	km	SoC_L^*	SoC_H^*	IR_{FC}^* (A)
WLTC 3	696	26	70	54
WLTC 2	908	29	69	50
NEDC	736	26	69	45

Table 4: Parameters EMS type 1

Drive cycle	km	SoC _L	SoC _H	IR _{FC} (A)
WLTC 3	661	25	45	60
WLTC 2	828	25	45	5
NEDC	714	25	45	40

Table 5: RBS Variables

To compare the performance of the PSO-optimized EMS type, we use the discrete optimized values from the RBS approach proposed in (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila, 2022). Both, parameters, values and kilometers traveled by using the RBS strategy, are presented in Table 5. As it can be seen, for all the driving cycle under test, the vehicle range has a noticeable improvement, increasing 80 km for WLTC class 2, 36 km for WLTC class 3 and 22 km for the drive cycle NEDC, comparing the results from Table 4 with the ones from Table 5.

Using the PSO optimization, we also compute the best set of parameters for the EMS Type 2 aiming to maximize the achieved range for each of the driving cycles tested for the EMS Type 1. In this paper we use three levels for the hydrogen tank, while it is possible to extend the results for different levels. In Figure 9 we show how the parameters $SoC_{L^*}(l)$ (top), $SoC_{H^*}(l)$ (middle) and $IR_{FC^*}(l)$ (bottom) evolve while the algorithm progresses, getting closer to the optimum values. Note how the parameters follow their own trajectories apparently independent from the other ones. This clearly evidences on how complex a discrete parameter tuning could be for this multi-level system. At the same time, in Figure 10, it can be seen how the range achieved by the vehicle suffer a big increase while the iterations advance. The results we showed in Figure 9 and Figure 10 were obtained applying the drive cycle WLTC class 3. We omitted the figures for the drive cycles WLTC class 2 and NEDC because the algorithm behavior is similar to the drive cycle WLTC class 3.

Figure 9: PSO-evolution (EMS Type 2)

Figure 10: Range PSO-evolution (EMS Type 2)

Using the set of optimized parameters from the PSO, in Figure 11.a (top plot) we present the SoC evolution for this scenario using the drive cycle WLTC class 3. At the beginning the battery supply almost the whole current demanded by the motor traveling 62 km in purely battery-supplied mode until the SoC level reaches 53 %. At this moment, the FC start operating (SC mode) supplying 15 A to keep the SoC level between 55 %

and 66 % during 204 km. After that, the FC increase the IR_{FC} to 52 A and the SoC level goes up 87 % and then the battery starts in CD until the level SoC reaches 17 %. After that, the SoC level is increased to 85 % and is kept for 161 km with an IR_{FC} of 43 A. Finally, when the hydrogen is over, the battery starts to supply the total energy of the vehicle during 117 km until it reaches the SoC_{min} . This multi-level operation of the EMS Type 2, allows to increase the achieved range from 697 km to 717 km, compared to the EMS Type 1 described before. In Figure 11 it is also shown the SoC-evolution (top plot) and the hydrogen tank level (bottom plot) for every drive cycle (WLTC 3 (a), WLTC 2 (b) and NEDC (c)) where it can be easily differentiated the three operation zones corresponding to the three hydrogen levels. It is important to remark that in the last track, for all the drives cycles, the battery SoC is increased around 80%, keeping this level until the hydrogen is over, this conditions help to increase the range of the vehicle because the SoC in this level allows to finish the travel in electric mode for a long period time. At the end of level 3, the battery supplies the total current demanded. In this point if the current required is higher than the maximum battery current, the battery gives this amount of current.

Figure 11: Battery SoC time & H₂ Tank evolution EMS Type 2. (WLTC class 3- WLTC class 2-NEDC)

The full set of parameters and kilometers travelled for the three driving cycles are summarized in Table 6. As it can be seen, it has been achieved an improvement for the three driving cycles under test compared to the EMS Type 1 results from Table 4 and then to the RBS approach from (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila,2022). Specifically, the improvement is of 20, 26 and 44 kilometers for the WLTC class 3, class 2 and NEDC driving cycles respectively when compared to the results from Table 4.

Drive cycle	km	Tank level	SoC _L *	SoC _H *	IR _{FC} * (A)
WLTC 3	717	High	53	66	15
		Medium	17	87	52
		Low	85	85	43
WLTC 2	934	High	56	82	44
		Medium	41	46	33
		Low	86	86	24
NEDC	758	High	28	83	12
		Medium	48	71	39
		Low	89	89	42

Table 6: Optimized parameters and achieved range for the EMS type 2 with different driving cycles.

SCENARIO 1. FC-PHEV

In order to get the configuration for FC-PHEV the EMS type 1 is used. With these rules, the PSO finds the control variables and selects the low level of SoC until the battery works as a primary source of energy, after this level is reached, the FC start to work to keep the SoC level and give the current demanded by the motor. This condition is keeping until the route is finished or the hydrogen is over. It is remarkable that the values of SoC_L* and SoC_H* given by the optimization algorithm in this configuration have small range between each other being almost the same value, therefore the IR_{FC}* is used to keep the level SoC computed. To get the plug-in configuration the constraints described in Equation 3 are redefined to get the optimum low SoC level. Therefore, the bounds for this powertrain configuration are:

$$\begin{aligned}
0.1 &\leq \text{SoC}_L^*(l) \leq 0.3 \\
0.1 &\leq \text{SoC}_H^*(l) \leq 0.3
\end{aligned}
\tag{4}$$

With the constraints shown above, we can guarantee that the energy from the battery is used first. The optimization algorithm returned the SoC level and the IR_{FC} where the vehicle reached the maximum range. To test how applying the PSO over the rules can improve the range of the vehicle, the simulation is made up to the time that the hydrogen tank is empty. Figure 12 shows how SoC_L (top), SoC_H (middle) and the IR_{FC} (bottom) update their values at the same time that the range increases (see Figure 13) as the algorithm progresses. Furthermore, the values of SoC_L and SoC_H are within the bounds defined in in Equation 4.

Figure 12: PSO-evolution

Figure 13: Range PSO-evolution

In Figure 14 it is shown the SoC trajectory for FC-PHEV. For all the drive cycles, the SoC_{L^*} values coincide around 28 % before using the FC as a primary source of energy to move the vehicle. Results are summarized in Table 7, displaying that from this test an increment of the range for every drive cycle is obtained if compared with the RBS proposed in (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila,2022). For the drive cycle WLTC class 3 an increase of 8 % is achieved when the battery is discharge until 27 % SoC and an IR_{FC}^* of 64 A is necessary to keep this SoC level. The total range is 710 km, 50 km more that the EMS configuration without using the optimization algorithm (RBS). For the drives cycles WLTC class 2 and NEDC an increase of 7 % and 5 % is achieved respectively.

Figure 14: Battery SoC- FC-PHEV Powertrain

Drive cycle	SoC_{L^*}	SoC_{H^*}	IR_{FC}^* (A)	km PSO	km RBS
WLTC 3	27	27	64	710	665
WLTC 2	28	28	52	886	830
NEDC	27	27	27	735	703

Table 7: Parameters FC-PHEV Powertrain

SCENARIO 2. FC-EREV

To show the optimization approach explained above where the objective is the hydrogen consumption minimization, the simulation is configured to run 450 km. In this case, for every drive cycle used a time simulation is defined to achieve the proposed kilometers to cover the route and the constraints defined in Scenario 1 to force the range extender behavior are keeping. In this sense, the algorithm computed the best parameter configuration for the short route under each drive cycle. To prove the performance of the parameters computed by the optimization algorithm, the hydrogen consumed in the tank is compared with the hydrogen consumed results obtained from the configuration powertrain proposed by (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila,2022). In Table 8 it is shown the configuration applied for each drive cycle. From this table the hydrogen mass consumed in the tank is shown, where the parameters returned by the PSO demonstrated an improvement with respect to RBS parameters for the hydrogen consumed under the same driver conditions. The optimization algorithm achieves a improvement of 3 % to the drive cycle WLTC class 3, 8 % and 7 % to the drive cycles WLTC class 2 and NEDC respectively.

For this scenario is applied the EMS type 2 configuration in order to compare the performance with the EMS type 1 and the RBS. Under this configuration the amount of hydrogen consumed in the tank is less than the hydrogen consumed when EMS type 1 is used for the same route, this is because, in a short path, it is better to use the electricity stored in the battery than hydrogen. Accordingly, the optimization algorithm gives priority to spend first the battery and then keep the SoC level assigned with the IR_{FC^*} computed. Results are summarized in Table 9 and it can be observed that under this configuration the hydrogen consumption is improved between 8 % and 11 % respect to EMS type 1 and 11 % and 19 % compared with the RBS, according to the drive cycle used to cover the route.

Drive cycle	SoC _L *	SoC _H *	IR _{FC} * (A)	kg · H ₂ PSO	kg · H ₂ RBS
WLTC 3	10	47	43	3.72	3.83
WLTC 2	10	52	68	2.95	3.22
NEDC	10	57	59	3.36	3.60

Table 8: Parameters for H2 minimization

Drive cycle	kg · H ₂	Tank level	SoC _L *	SoC _H *	IR _{FC} * (A)
WLTC 3	3.42	High	39	83	48
		Medium	10	10	27
		Low	29	55	27
WLTC 2	2.62	High	28	59	47
		Medium	10	25	35
		Low	29	33	63
NEDC	3.28	High	12	12	55
		Medium	10	13	9
		Low	14	18	30

Table 9: Parameters for H2 minimization EMS type 2

In Figure 15 it is shown the hydrogen tank level evolution to the drive cycle WLTC class 3, the simulation applies the same time in all the EMS configurations. The best performance for this scenario occurs under

the EMS type 2, the level tank for this configuration reached a level of 40 % for the route selected while the hydrogen tank achieves levels of 33 % and 32 % for EMS type 1 and RBS respectively. This supposes a great improve in the hydrogen consumption, demonstrating that the vehicle can travel the same route using lees hydrogen.

Figure 15: Hydrogen tank evolution (WLTC class 3)

SCENARIO 2. FC-PHEV

The optimization algorithm is used in this case to minimize the hydrogen consumption for a FC-PHEV using the cost function defined in Equation 2, covering a route of 450 km. In this scenario the control variables are looking for reducing hydrogen consumption. To get the powertrain configuration, the optimization algorithm must find the lowest SoC level that must reach the battery before the FC starts to work. In this sense, the optimization algorithm finds this value between 10 % and 30 % of the level (using the constrains defined in Equation 4), these limits are selected to guarantee that the battery is used without causing damage and the energy stored is used completely. The simulation run with a high SoC level of 90 %, therefore it starts in CD mode until reaches the low level given by the PSO. Figure 16 shows the SoC evolution to the EMS parameter configuration found by the PSO against to the RBS parameters proposed by (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila,2022). Note that with the parameters computed by the PSO the SoC is sustained in 17 % while with the RBS it oscillates between 20 % and 25 %. On another hand, Figure 17 shows the hydrogen tank level, it is important to focus that, on equal driving conditions, with the parameters computed by the PSO, less hydrogen is consumed. This implies an improvement of 5 % when the RBS parameters are applied.

Figure 16: Battery SoC-evolution for FC-PHEV

Figure 17: H₂-evolution for FC-PHEV WLTC 3

To test our proposal under different conditions, we also run the optimization algorithm for two extra driving cycles NEDC and WLTC class 2, results are shown in Table 10, for the drives cycle WLTC class 2 and NEDC the results thrown by the PSO coincide in discharge the battery until 10 % of level, under this configuration the hydrogen consumed in the tank is 2.59 and 3.28 kilograms to WLTC class 2 and NEDC demonstrating an improve of 5 % for both driver cycles.

Drive cycle	SoC _L *	SoC _H *	I _{RFC} *	kg · H ₂ PSO	kg · H ₂ RBS
WLTC 3	17	17	55	3.41	3.58
WLTC 2	10	10	14	2.59	2.74
NEDC	10	10	9	3.28	3.45

Table 10: Parameters for FC-PHEV powertrain

DISCUSSION

The summary of results obtained is presented in Tables 11 and . from Table 11 are shown the kilometers traveled until the battery reaches the low SoC level and the hydrogen tank is empty, for each powertrain configuration and each EMS. Note that, for FC-EREV depending on the EMS type applied a different range is given. From table, the drive cycle WLTC 3 are gotten ranges to 696 km and 717 when the EMS type 1 and 2 are used, respectively. When these ranges are compared with the results reported by (Alvarez Fernandez and Perez-Davila,2022), where RBS was proposed, with the new EMS proposed in this article an increase to the range is achieved. While the RBS achieved a range to 661 km, using the optimization algorithm together with the rules proposed to EMS type 1 y EMS type 2, the parameters computed by the PSO obtains an improvement in the kilometers traveled. The drive cycle WLTC 3 of 717 km and 758 km to the drive cycle NEDC cycle, using the EMS type 2 and the optimization algorithm, this supposed an improved 8 % with respect to the RBS. It is important to highlight that considerer the hydrogen stored in the tank as a variable to the PSO allowed an improved of 3 % of the kilometers traveled compared with EMS type 1. Results confirm the advantage of the hybridization over the vehicle autonomy, mix the energy from a storage

element such a battery with the FC, allow overcome the range trouble that BEV has, hence the EMSs proposed demonstrated the advantages to applied an optimization algorithm to the rules, accordingly with the variables returned by the optimization algorithm for the EMS type 1 the vehicle has a better performance when the battery discharge occurs between 20 % and 30 % SoC before starting to recharge, when the range extended configuration is used. However, when the EMS type 2 is used, for all drive cycles, the battery is used to move the vehicle in the first track until reached a SoC levels between 30 % and 50 % before the SC is active. With this EMS configuration is denoted that the variation to the IR_{FC} according to the level of the tank help to improve the range by adding more kilometers to the travel. On the other hand, for FC-PHEV the EMS type 2 was not used, due to in this powertrain the battery works until a low SoC level, therefore it is unnecessary define the works zone for the hydrogen tank, however applying the optimization algorithm to the rules proposed for the EMS type 1, the vehicle improves the range, getting an increase of 7 % and 5 % with respect to RBS without us the optimization algorithm, depending on the drive cycle used, the parameters given by the PSO to this powertrain, keep the low SoC level around 27 % until the hydrogen is over, then the SoC level fall until 10 %, this indicate that the vehicle cannot move. In general, our approach can achieve ranges between 697 km to 908 km depending on the powertrain model and the drive cycle used. This set of values is consistent when compared with the commercial models such as the Hyundai Nexso (Hyundai, 2022) or other proposals (Molina et al., 2021) that achieves ranges between 600 and 700 km.

Drive Cycle	Vehicle Type	km		
		EMS 1	EMS 2	RBS
WLTC 3	FC-EREV	696	717	665
	FC-PHEV	710	N/A	661
WLTC 2	FC-EREV	908	931	830
	FC-PHEV	886	N/A	828
NEDC	FC-EREV	736	758	714
	FC-PHEV	735	N/A	703

Table 11: Summary of range results

The results from Scenario 2 are shown in Table 12, the hydrogen mass consumed when the parameters and the EMS type 2 configuration are used, it reported a reduction compared with RBS and the EMS type 1. For the FC-EREV the hydrogen mass consumed to cover the selected route are 3.72 kg and 3.83 kg for EMS type 1 and RBS respectively, what means 8 % and 12 % more hydrogen consumed under the same driving conditions. The same behavior occurs to the drive cycles WLTC 2 and NEDC, the lowest mass consumed is obtained when the EMS type 2 is used. The hydrogen consumption ($kgH_2/100km$) of commercial vehicles are 0.87 $kgH_2/100km$ in the Renault Kangoo ZE and 0.9 $kgH_2/100km$ in the case of Hyundai Nexso, in this approach the best performance is found when the powertrain uses the EMS type 2, it varies between 0.60 $kgH_2/100km$ and 0.78 depending on the drive cycle and the vehicle type selected. Results are summarized in Table 12, where it can be observed that EMS type 1 hydrogen consumption obtained varies from 0.62 $kgH_2/100km$ to 0.80 $kgH_2/100km$, these results demonstrated that the rules together with the optimization algorithm reduce the hydrogen consumption when it is compared with RBS configuration where the consumption takes value of 0.85 $kgH_2/100km$ when the drive cycle WLTC class 3 is used. Talking

about the total energy consumed (Wh/km), the parameters got for both EMS (type 1 and 2), allowing a reduction of the energy consumed compared with rules and the parameters not optimized. The best energy distribution is found using the EMS type 2, where reductions of 2 % 6 % and 11 % are achieved. Therefore, the results obtained for the consumption of hydrogen and for the total energy consumed are coherent and in line with the consumptions found in the literature (Molina et al., 2021) and with the commercial models found in the automotive industry.

Drive Cycle	Vehicle Type	Energy Consumption Wh/km			H ₂ Consumption kgH ₂ /100km			kg · H ₂		
		EMS 1	EMS 2	RBS	EMS 1	EMS 2	RBS	EMS 1	EMS 2	RBS
WLTC 3	FC-EREV	585	572	613	0.80	0.78	0.85	3.72	3.42	3.83
	FC-PHEV	574	N/A	617	0.79	N/A	0.85	3.41	N/A	3.58
WLTC 2	FC-EREV	449	438	493	0.62	0.60	0.68	2.95	2.62	3.22
	FC-PHEV	458	N/A	492	0.63	N/A	0.67	2.59	N/A	2.74
NEDC	FC-EREV	554	538	571	0.76	0.74	0.78	3.36	3.28	3.6
	FC-PHEV	555	N/A	580	0.76	N/A	0.8	2.28	N/A	3.45

Table 12: Summary of results: energy and H₂ consumption

CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the present research work was the implementation of algorithms that allow to optimize the vehicle performance, increasing the range of hydrogen hybrid vehicles managed through different energy management systems. It is evident that the improvement in range implies a reduction in energy consumption and consequently in GHG emissions. In order to find the best performance for each powertrain analyzed, it has been designed a rule-based strategy that works together with the optimization algorithm to maximize the range or to reduce the energy consumption. The results obtained show the advantage of including both, the optimization algorithm together with a rule-based strategy, achieving an improvement in the vehicle range when applying different speed profiles. It is important to remark that the EMSs proposed for the powertrains object of study improve the efficiency in energy consumption with respect to apply a rule-based strategy without using the optimization algorithm. The battery capacity of the powertrain models is 19 kWh, this increase of the battery capacity with respect to the original vehicle, helps to get a reduction in the hydrogen consumption, currently, this is an advantage due to the limited number of hydrogen refueling stations. However, with the ranges/consumptions achieved, the hybrid vehicles propelled by hydrogen and electricity optimized with algorithms have proven to be a good alternative to replace fossil fuel powered vehicles and overcome the range problems.

As a final note, the authors hope that this work will contribute to understand the alternatives that might contribute to popularize other powertrain technologies and fuels that could contribute towards the decarbonization of road transport.

REFERENCES

- ACEA, 2021. European automobile manufactures association. URL: <https://www.acea.be/press-releases/article/fuel-types-of-new-cars-battery-electric-5.7-hybrid-18.4-petrol-42.2-market>.
- Ahmed Fathy, Hegazy Rezk, Ahmed M. Nassef, Robust hydrogen-consumption-minimization strategy based salp swarm algorithm for energy management of fuel cell/supercapacitor/batteries in highly fluctuated load condition, *Renewable Energy*, Volume 139, 2019, 147-160.
- Álvarez Fernández, R., Corbera Caraballo, S., Beltrán Cilleruelo, F., Lozano, J.A., 2018. Fuel optimization strategy for hydrogen fuel cell range extender vehicles applying genetic algorithms. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 81, 655–668. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.08.047>.
- Álvarez Fernández, R., Cilleruelo, F.B., Martínez, I.V., 2016. A new approach to battery powered electric vehicles: A hydrogen fuel-cell-based range extender system. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 41, 4808–4819. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.01.035>.
- Álvarez Fernández, R., Perez-Davila, O., 2022. Fuel cell hybrid vehicles and their role in the decarbonization of road transport. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 342, 30902. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130902>.
- Brand, C., Cluzel, C., Anable, J., 2017. Modeling the uptake of plug-in vehicles in a heterogeneous car market using a consumer segmentation approach. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* 97, 121–136. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2017.01.017>.
- Carignano, M., Roda, V., Costa-Castello, R., Valiño, L., Lozano, A., Barreras, F., 2019. Assessment of energy management in a fuel cell/battery hybrid vehicle. *IEEE Access* 7, 16110–16122. doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2889738](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2889738).
- Fernandez, R., 2021. Stochastic analysis of future scenarios for battery electric vehicle deployment and the upgrade of the electricity generation system in Spain. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 316, 128101. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128101>.
- Friedlingstein, P., Andrew, R.M., Rogelj, J., Peters, G.P., Canadell, J.G., Knutti, R., Luderer, G., Raupach, M.R., Schaeffer, M., van Vuuren, D.P., Le Quéré, C., 2014. Persistent growth of CO₂ emissions and implications for reaching climate targets. *Nature Geosci* 7, 709–715.
- Hyundai (2022). Hyundai Nexo pila combustible de hidrogeno. URL: <https://s7g10.scene7.com/is/content/hyundaiautoever/catalogo-NEXOpdf-1>.
- IEA, 2021. International Energy Agency. URL: <https://www.iea.org/>. Javaid, A., Creutzig, F., Bamberg, S., 2020. Determinants of low-carbon transport mode adoption: systematic review of reviews. *Environmental Research Letters* 15, 103002.
- Liu, Y., Li, J., Chen, Z., Qin, D., Zhang, Y., 2019. Research on a multi-objective hierarchical prediction energy management strategy for range extended fuel cell vehicles. *Journal of Power Sources* 429, 55–66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.04.118>.
- Mahmoodi-k, M., Montazeri, M., Madanipour, V., 2021. Simultaneous multi-objective optimization of a phev power management system and component sizing in real world traffic condition. *Energy* 233, 121111. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121111>.
- Molina, S., Novella, R., Pla, B., Lopez-Juarez, M., 2021. Optimization and sizing of a fuel cell range extender vehicle for passenger car applications in driving cycle conditions. *Applied Energy* 285, 116469. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116469>.
- NEESC, 2018. The Northeast Electrochemical Energy Storage Cluster. URL: <http://neesc.org/>.

- O'Hayre, R., Cha, S.W., Colella, W., Prinz, F., 2016. Chapter 6: Fuel Cell Modeling. chapter 6. pp. 203–236. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119191766.ch6>.
- Rahman, I., Vasant, P., Singh, B., Abdullah-Al-Wadud, M., 2015. Swarm intelligence-based optimization for PHEV charging stations. IGI Global. chapter 12. pp. 374–405.
- Rezk, H., Nassef, A.M., Abdelkareem, M.A., Alami, A.H., Fathy, A., 2021. Comparison among various energy management strategies for reducing hydrogen consumption in a hybrid fuel cell / supercapacitor / battery system. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 46, 6110–6126. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.11.195>.
- Samsatli, S., Samsatli, N.J., 2019. The role of renewable hydrogen and inter- seasonal storage in decarbonizing heat – comprehensive optimization of future renewable energy value chains. *Applied Energy* 233-234, 854–893. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.09.159>.
- Sharaf, O.Z., Orhan, M.F., 2014. An overview of fuel cell technology: Fundamentals and applications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 32, 810–853. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.01.012>.
- Sorlei, I.S., Bizon, N., Thounthong, P., Varlam, M., Carcadea, E., Culcer, M., Iliescu, M., Raceanu, M., 2021. Fuel cell electric vehicles—a brief review of current topologies and energy management strategies. *Energies* 14. doi: 10.3390/en14010252.
- Sulaiman, N., Hannan, M., Mohamed, A., Ker, P., Majlan, E., Wan Daud, W., 2018. Optimization of energy management system for fuel-cell hybrid electric vehicles: Issues and recommendations. *Applied Energy* 228, 2061–2079. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.0.
- Un-Noor, F., Sanjeevikumar, P., Mihet-Popa, L., Mollah, M., Hossain, E., 2017. A comprehensive study of key electric vehicle (EV) components, technologies, challenges, impacts, and future direction of development. *Energies* 10. doi: 10.3390/en10081217.
- Vasant, P.M., Rahman, I., Singh, B.S.M., Abdullah-Al-Wadud, M., 2016. Optimal power allocation scheme for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles using swarm intelligence techniques. *Cogent Engineering* 3, 1203083. doi:10.1080/23311916.2016.1203083.
- Weiss, M., Patel, M.K., Junginger, M., Perujo, A., Bonnel, P., van Grootveld, G., 2012. On the electrification of road transport - learning rates and price forecasts for hybrid-electric and battery-electric vehicles. *Energy Policy* 48, 374–393. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.05.038>. special Section: Frontiers of Sustainability.
- Zhang, Y., Wei, C., Liu, Y., Chen, Z., Hou, Z., Xu, N., 2021. A novel optimal power management strategy for plug-in hybrid electric vehicle with improved adaptability to traffic conditions. *Journal of Power Sources* 489, 229512. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.229512>.
- Zhou, Y., Ravey, A., Péra, M.C., 2020. Multi-mode predictive energy management for fuel cell hybrid electric vehicles using Markov driving pattern recognizer. *Applied Energy* 258, 114057. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114057>.
- Wang, D. T. (2018). Particle swarm optimization algorithm: an overview. *Soft Comput*, 387–408.